

SPIRIT CHECKLIST FOR REPORTING PROTOCOL OF “QUEST: Quality of Life and Evaluation of Survival in Treatment of Bladder Cancer”

Section/Item	Item No	SPIRIT Checklist Item	Response (QUEST protocol)
Title	1	Descriptive title identifying the study design, population, interventions (if applicable), and trial acronym (if any).	“QUEST: Quality of Life and Evaluation of Survival in Treatment of Bladder Cancer” – a clear title indicating this is a prospective cohort study using PROMs in bladder cancer patients.
Trial registration	2a	Trial identifier and registry name. If not yet registered, name of intended registry.	Registered in Clinical Trials Registry – India (CTRI) as CTRI/2025/03/083504.
Trial registration	2b	All items from the World Health Organization Trial Registration Data Set.	The CTRI record includes all required fields (study title, sponsors, recruitment status, outcomes, etc.), as per WHO Trial Registration Data Set.
Protocol version	3	Date and version identifier of the protocol.	Version 1.0 (date: April 2025).
Funding / Grant information	4	Sources and types of financial, material, and other support for the study.	No external funding or grants were involved. The study is supported by institutional resources at CNCI and contributions of the authors.
Roles and responsibilities	5a	Names, affiliations, and roles of protocol contributors.	All authors and their affiliations are listed on the manuscript cover page. The author contributions section details their roles.
Roles and responsibilities (sponsor)	5b	Name and contact information for the trial sponsor.	Sponsor: Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute (CNCI), Kolkata, India (the institution where all authors work). CNCI is the sponsor/institution overseeing the study; no external sponsor.
Roles and responsibilities (funders)	5c	Role of study sponsor and funders (if any) in design, data collection/analysis, writing, and submission decision.	The sponsor (CNCI) provided infrastructure and oversight via the Institutional Ethics Committee but had no role in data collection, analysis,

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			interpretation, or the decision to publish. All authors independently authored the manuscript.
Roles and responsibilities (committees)	5d	Composition, roles, and responsibilities of coordinating center, steering committee, endpoint committee, data management team, etc.	Not applicable beyond the study team. There is no external coordinating center or steering committee. Oversight of data collection and analysis is by the principal investigators (JC and DG).
Background and rationale	6a	Description of research question and justification, including summary of relevant studies.	The introduction (Background) summarizes the evidence on RC vs. TMT, rationale for QoL comparison, and gaps in existing Indian data.
Background and rationale	6b	Explanation for choice of comparators.	The “comparators” are the two treatment approaches (RC and TMT). Since patients self-select treatment, this is an observational comparison. We will compare these groups to evaluate real-world outcomes.
Objectives	7	Specific objectives or hypotheses.	Clearly stated: primary objective is to compare QoL outcomes (using BCI and QLQ-C30) between RC and TMT. Secondary objectives include comparing OS/PFS and correlating PROM scores with survival.
Trial design	8	Description of trial design (e.g., parallel group, cohort), allocation ratio, framework (superiority, etc.).	Prospective, single-center observational cohort (parallel groups: RC vs. TMT). No allocation or randomization (patients self-select). The framework is descriptive/comparative (hypothesized differences in QoL and survival).
Study setting	9	Description of study settings and list of sites.	Single tertiary academic hospital (Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute, Kolkata, India). All patients recruited and treated at this center.

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Eligibility criteria	10	Inclusion and exclusion criteria for participants (and centres if applicable).	Inclusion: Adult patients (≥ 18 years) with biopsy-proven MIBC (cT2–T4aN0M0) who are eligible for either RC or TMT. Exclusion: Metastatic disease, prior bladder cancer treatment, severe comorbidity contraindicating either therapy, or inability to complete questionnaires.
Interventions	11a	Interventions for each group with sufficient detail to allow replication.	Not applicable (observational study). Patients undergo either standard RC (with urinary diversion) or standard TMT (maximal TURBT + chemoradiation) per institutional protocols. No experimental interventions are administered by the study.
Interventions (discontinuation)	11b	Criteria for discontinuing or modifying interventions for a given participant.	Not applicable. Treatment modifications (e.g., stopping chemotherapy) follow routine clinical practice, independent of study protocol.
Interventions (adherence)	11c	Strategies to improve adherence to intervention protocols and any procedures for monitoring adherence.	Standard clinical follow-up and counseling are used to encourage patients to complete therapy. Adherence to radiotherapy or chemotherapy is tracked via medical records. (No study-specific adherence interventions.)
Interventions (concomitant care)	11d	Relevant concomitant care permitted or prohibited during the trial.	All standard supportive care and medications are permitted as needed. There are no prohibited concomitant treatments; patients may receive routine medications (e.g., antibiotics, transfusions) per clinician judgment.
Outcomes	12	Primary, secondary, and other outcomes, including measurement specifics and time points.	Primary outcomes: QoL scores (urinary, bowel, sexual, and global domains) measured by BCI and QLQ-C30 at baseline and at 6, 12, 24, and 36

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			months post-treatment. Secondary outcomes: OS (time from treatment to death) and PFS. Outcomes are clearly defined in the protocol, with plan to analyze changes over time.
Participant timeline	13	Time schedule of enrolment, interventions, assessments, and visits.	Schedule: Patients are enrolled before treatment, then followed with PROM assessments at baseline (pre-treatment), 6 mo, 12 mo, 24 mo, and 36 mo. Survival status is updated continuously. A schematic timeline is provided in the protocol and in Figure 1 of the manuscript.
Sample size	14	Estimated number of participants and how it was determined, including assumptions.	Target sample size is 94 (approximately 47 per group), based on detecting a medium effect size (Cohen's $d \sim 0.6$) in QoL scores with 80% power and alpha 0.05. Calculations assume up to 10% dropout. This calculation and assumptions are detailed in the Statistical Analysis Plan.
Recruitment	15	Strategies for achieving adequate enrollment to reach target sample size.	All eligible MIBC patients at CNCI will be invited to participate. With ~100 eligible cases per year treated at our center, a 12-month recruitment window is feasible. Study information is provided by the clinical team, and investigators follow up to encourage enrollment. No incentives are used. Recruitment progress will be monitored monthly.
Allocation (Sequence generation)	16a	Method of generating the allocation sequence.	Not applicable (no random allocation).
Allocation (Concealment mechanism)	16b	Mechanism of implementing the allocation sequence.	Not applicable.

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Allocation (Implementation)	16c	Who will generate the allocation sequence, who will enroll participants, and who will assign interventions.	Not applicable. Patients self-select treatment after counseling; the study does not assign interventions.
Blinding (masking)	17a	Who will be blinded after assignment to interventions (e.g., participants, care providers, outcome assessors) and how.	Not applicable. Neither patients nor clinicians are blinded to treatment. PROMs are self-reported by patients at home or in clinic without blinding. Data analysis will be conducted by statisticians aware of group assignments.
Blinding (unblinding)	17b	If blinded, circumstances for unblinding and procedure.	Not applicable (open-label observational design).
Data collection methods	18a	Plans for assessment and collection of outcomes, baseline, and other data, including processes to promote data quality and description of instruments.	PROMs (BCI and QLQ-C30) are completed by patients at scheduled visits or via secure electronic surveys. Clinical and survival data (e.g., pathology, imaging, date of death) are extracted from medical records. Study staff are trained in data collection. Data quality is ensured by double data entry and regular consistency checks.
Data collection (retention)	18b	Plans to promote participant retention and complete follow-up, including outcome data for those who discontinue or deviate.	Patients will receive reminders for follow-up visits and surveys via phone/email. A dropout log will record reasons for loss to follow-up. We will attempt to collect minimum outcome data (e.g., survival status) for patients who withdraw, through phone follow-up or public records. Missing PRO data will be handled in analysis with appropriate methods.
Data management	19	Plans for data entry, coding, security, and storage, including data quality processes.	Data will be entered into a secure, password-protected database. Double data entry will be used for PROM responses. Identifiers will be stored separately from study data. Regular data audits (range and logic checks) will be performed. Electronic data backups are maintained. All procedures comply with institutional data security policies.

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Statistical methods	20a	Statistical methods for analyzing primary and secondary outcomes.	Primary analysis: QoL scores will be compared between groups at each time point using t-tests or nonparametric tests, and over time using repeated-measures ANOVA or mixed models. Survival outcomes will be analyzed by Kaplan–Meier estimation and log-rank tests. Multivariable Cox regression will adjust for covariates. Details of these methods are provided in the Statistical Analysis Plan (supplement).
Statistical methods (additional)	20b	Methods for any additional analyses (e.g., subgroup, adjusted analyses).	Pre-specified subgroup analyses include stratification by urinary diversion type (in RC) and baseline factors (age, comorbidity). Adjusted analyses using regression models will control for potential confounders (e.g., stage, performance status).
Statistical methods (analysis pop)	20c	Definition of analysis population (intention-to-treat, per-protocol) and methods for handling missing data.	Primary analysis will use all enrolled patients (“as-treated” observational cohort). Secondary “per-protocol” analyses will exclude major protocol violations. Missing data will be addressed by multiple imputation when appropriate; last observation carried forward will not be used for PROMs.
Monitoring (Data Monitoring)	21a	Composition and role of Data Monitoring Committee (DMC), or explanation if none.	No independent DMC is planned due to the low-risk, observational nature of the study. The principal investigators (JC and DG) will internally monitor study progress and safety. Any serious protocol deviations will be reported to the IEC per institutional policy.
Monitoring (Interim analyses)	21b	Description of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines.	No formal interim efficacy or futility analyses are planned. As an observational study of standard treatments, there are no stopping rules. Enrollment and data collection will continue until targets are met.
Harms	22	Plans for collecting, assessing, reporting, and managing	Adverse events (AEs) related to cancer treatment (e.g., surgical complications,

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		adverse events and unintended effects of interventions or trial conduct.	radiation toxicity) will be recorded from medical records. These are managed according to standard clinical practice. Study staff will record any serious AEs in the database. There are no study-specific interventions, so only treatment-related AEs are captured. Serious AEs will be reported to the IEC as required.
Auditing	23	Frequency and procedures for auditing trial conduct, if any, independent of investigators/sponsor.	No external audit is planned. Internal audits of data collection and adherence to protocol will be performed periodically by the study coordinators. The IEC may also review the study conduct during annual continuing review.
Research ethics approval	24	Plans for seeking research ethics committee/IRB approval.	Approval has been obtained from the IEC of CNCI (Ref. IEC/CNCI/2025/001) before starting the study. Any future protocol amendments will also be submitted for IEC approval before implementation.
Protocol amendments	25	Plans for communicating important protocol modifications (changes to eligibility, outcomes, analyses) to all relevant parties.	Any important amendments will be documented with dates and rationale. Changes to outcomes or analysis plans will be communicated to the CTRI registry, the IEC, trial participants (if affected), and updated in any publications or registry entries.
Consent or assent (procedures)	26a	Who will obtain informed consent or assent and how.	Informed consent will be obtained by the principal investigators or trained study staff in a private setting. The written consent form (provided in extended data) will be explained thoroughly, and participants will have time to ask questions. Consent will be documented in writing before any study procedures.

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Consent or assent (additional)	26b	Additional consent provisions for collection/use of participant data and biological specimens in ancillary studies, if applicable.	Not applicable. No biological specimens are collected or stored for ancillary studies.
Confidentiality	27	How personal information about participants will be collected, shared, and maintained to protect confidentiality.	Participant identity will be protected by assigning study IDs. Personal identifiers (names, contact details) will be stored separately from study data. Data files will not contain any direct identifiers. Only study investigators will have access to the linkage key. Any published data will be aggregated so individuals cannot be identified.
Declaration of interests	28	Financial and other competing interests for investigators and study sites.	All authors have declared no financial or non-financial competing interests related to this study (see Competing Interests statement).
Access to data	29	Statement of who will have access to the final dataset, and disclosure of any contractual agreements limiting access.	The de-identified final dataset will be accessible to the study investigators (authors) for analysis. There are no restrictions or contracts limiting data access. Any future sharing of individual-level data will comply with ethical and privacy requirements and will require approval by the IEC and appropriate data use agreements.
Ancillary and post-trial care	30	Provisions for ancillary and post-trial care, and for compensation to those who suffer harm from trial participation.	All patients will continue to receive standard medical care at the treating center. The study does not provide additional clinical interventions post-trial. There are no formal compensation provisions beyond the standard institutional policy for research-related injuries or harms; any harm related to routine treatment will be managed by the clinical team, and patients retain all

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			rights under applicable healthcare regulations.
Dissemination policy (results)	31a	Plans for communication of trial results to participants, healthcare professionals, the public, and other groups, including any publication restrictions.	Study results will be published in peer-reviewed open-access journals (as per F1000 policy) and presented at relevant conferences. Summaries of results will be shared with participants upon request. There are no publication restrictions. The protocol and results will also be uploaded to the CTRI registry and data repository (Zenodo) for transparency.
Dissemination policy (authorship)	31b	Authorship eligibility guidelines and intended use of professional writers.	Authorship will follow ICMJE criteria (contributions to design, data, analysis, writing). No professional medical writer is involved. All listed authors meet authorship criteria; no others contributed substantially who are not listed. No ghostwriting or honorary authorship will occur.
Dissemination policy (data sharing)	31c	Plans, if any, for granting public access to the full protocol, participant-level dataset, and statistical code.	The full protocol (this document) and extended materials (e.g., SPIRIT checklist, consent forms) are deposited on Zenodo under CC0 (data license). Participant-level dataset is not being made public due to privacy, but key aggregate data will be reported in publications. Statistical code (R scripts) used in analysis will be made available in a GitHub repository (to be linked on Zenodo deposit).
Informed consent materials	32	Model consent form and related documents given to participants and surrogates.	The full informed consent form and patient information sheet are provided as extended data on Zenodo (CC0) and briefly summarized in the Methods. These documents are adapted from institutional templates and include all required elements (purpose, procedures,

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			risks, benefits, confidentiality, voluntary participation).
Biological specimens	33	Plans for collection, evaluation, and storage of biological specimens for genetic/molecular analysis (current trial and future ancillary studies).	Not applicable. No biological specimens (e.g., blood, tissue) are collected for research purposes beyond routine pathological analysis.